

Statistical mechanics of solubility of non-polar gases in polar and non-polar solvents

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The cavity formation energy (CFE) which is equivalent to the free energy cost of insertion of a hard sphere solute in a hard sphere solvent, is calculated for benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water at 298 K. The solubility of non-polar gases He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe, and Rn in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water has been calculated with this CFE. The results agree well with the experimental values of Henry's law constant and molar free energy of solution. The method has also been used to calculate the hard sphere diameter of the solvents.

Considerable theoretical and experimental work have been done on the solubility of non-polar gases in non-polar solvents. Pierotti^{1,2} proposed a theory on the bases of scaled particle theory of Riess *et al.*^{3,4}. The theory used the reversible work required to introduce a solute molecule into a fluid. Pierotti assumed the equivalence of partial molar free energy (G_o) of cavity formation and the cavity formation energy (CFE). CFE is a substantial part of the total solvation energy for most molecular fluids^{5,6}. Pierotti compared the reversible work required [$\omega(r, \rho)$] to produce cavity in a fluid and the same required for macroscopic cavity formation in classical thermodynamics. This comparative calculation can be avoided as Matyushov and Ladanyi⁷ directly calculated the cavity formation energy from the exact geometrical relation valid for hard sphere fluids.

In the present communication the CFE expressions are used to calculate the solubility of the non-polar gases in some polar and non-polar solvents and calculations for these system are compared with the experimental results.

Theory :

The solubility of the non-polar gas solutes in polar and non-polar solvents can be calculated by considering the solution process to consists of two steps : (i) the creation of cavity in the solvent of suitable size to accommodate the solute molecules, and (ii) the introduction into the cavity the solute molecule which interacts with the solvent.

For extremely dilute solution, the Henry's law for solubility can be written as

$$\ln K_H = G_o/RT + G_i/RT + \ln (RT/V_1) \quad (1)$$

where G_o and G_i are the partial molar free energy for cavity formation and interaction respectively, V_1 is the molar volume of the solvent, R the gas constant, T the absolute temperature and K_H the Henry's law constant.

Calculation of the cavity formation energy (CFE) : The properties of hard sphere fluids follows from its geometry. Riess *et al.*^{3,4} calculated the reversible work required to introduce a spherical particle in a fluid from statistical mechanics. The probability of finding a position for a zero size solute in the solvent is just the volume fraction unoccupied by the solvent hard spheres and is $1 - \eta$, where $\eta = 1/6 \pi \rho \sigma^3$, ρ is the number density and σ_1 the hard sphere diameter of the solvent. Therefore the chemical potential are¹

$$\beta \mu_{\text{cav}}(0) = -\ln(1 - \eta) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } |\partial \beta \mu_{\text{cav}}(d)/\partial d|_{d=0} = 3\eta/1 - \eta \quad (3)$$

where $d = \sigma_1/\sigma_2$, σ_2 is the hard sphere diameter of the solute. If the solute size is taken to be infinite the cavity formation energy should be the volume work against the liquid pressure, i.e.

$$\beta \mu_{\text{cav}}(d \rightarrow \infty) = \beta P(\pi d^3 \sigma^3/6) = (\eta Z) d^3 \quad (4)$$

According to the scaled particle theory,

$$\lim_{d \rightarrow \infty} 1/3 d^2 [\partial \beta \mu_{\text{cav}}(d)/\partial d] = \eta Z \quad (5)$$

The BMCSL theory shows that

$$\beta \mu_{\text{cav}}^{\text{BMCSL}}(d) = 2\eta^3/(1 - \eta)^3 + 3\eta d^2 / (1 - \eta)^2 + 3\eta d (-d^2 + d + 1) / (1 - \eta) + (-2d^3 + 3d^2 - 1) \ln(1 - \eta) \quad (6)$$

This shows that the higher order terms of $\mu_{\text{cav}}(d)$ is proportional to d^3 . Hence the $\mu_{\text{cav}}(d)$ can be represented by polynomial,

$$\mu_{\text{cav}}(d) = \sum_{i=0}^3 a_i d^i \quad (7)$$

Z (compressibility), can be obtained from the Carnahan-

Stirling (CS) equation for hard sphere compressibility factor,

$$Z_{CS} = (1 + \eta + \eta^2 + \eta^3)/(1 - \eta)^3 \quad (8)$$

Substituting equations (7) and (8) in equations (2), (3), (4) and (6), the cavity formation energy can be written as

$$\beta\mu_{cav}(d) = -\ln(1 - \eta) + 3\eta d/(1 - \eta) + 3\eta(2 - \eta)/(1 + \eta)d^2/2(1 - \eta)^2 + (1 + \eta + \eta^2 + \eta^3)d^3/(1 - \eta)^3 \quad (9)$$

The last term is related to the hydrostatic pressure for gas solubility in incompressible liquids and neglected.

Evaluation of G_i : This term due to the soft part of potential may be considered as the free energy needed to introduce the solute molecule into cavity and was estimated⁵ as

$$G_i/RT = -16/3(\epsilon_{dis}^*/KT) - 8(\epsilon_{ind}^* + \epsilon_{dip}^*)/KT \quad (10)$$

where $\epsilon^* = \pi\rho\epsilon_i/6\sigma_{12}^3$.

The contribution of dispersion energy may be estimated by the expression,

$$C_{dis} = 4(\epsilon_1\epsilon_2)^{1/2}[(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)/2] \quad (11)$$

where ϵ_1, ϵ_2 are the energy parameter for Lennard-Jones (6-12) potential for the solvent and solute and σ_1 and σ_2 are the hard sphere diameter of the solvent and solute respectively.

The inductive energy parameter,

$$C_{ind} = \mu_1^2\alpha_2 + \mu_2^2\alpha_1 \quad (12)$$

where μ_1 and μ_2 are the dipole moment of the solvent and solute, and α_1 and α_2 are the polarisability of the solvent and solute respectively.

The dipole-dipole interaction constant,

$$C_{dip} = 2/3\mu_1\mu_2/KT \quad (13)$$

Substituting these values in the equation (10), we get,

(i) for non-polar gas in non-polar solvent :

$$G_i/RT = 32\pi\rho\epsilon_{1j}^{1/2}\sigma_{1j}^3/9KT \quad (14)$$

(ii) and for non-polar gas in polar solvent,

$$G_i/RT = 32\pi\rho\epsilon_{1j}^{1/2}\sigma_{1j}^3/9KT - 4\pi\rho\mu_1^2\alpha_2/3\sigma_{1j}^3KT \quad (15)$$

Combining these equations, the final general expression for gas solubility is

$$\ln K_H = -\ln(1 - \eta) + 3\eta d/(1 - \eta) + 3\eta(2 - \eta)/(1 + \eta)d^2/2(1 - \eta)^2 - 16/3(\epsilon_{ind}^*/KT) - 16/3(\epsilon_{dis}^*/KT) + \ln(RT/V_1) \quad (16)$$

Results and Discussion

Cavity formation energy of various liquid at 289 K shown in Fig. 1, in which dashed lines represent the cavity formation energy according to equation (9) and solid lines represent the cavity formation energy neglecting the hydrostatic contribution. The necessary molecular parameters are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Determination of Henry's law constant: The calculated Henry's law constant ($\ln K_H$) and Gibb's free energy of solution (ΔG_s) are compared with the experimental values in Table 3.

Fig. 1. Cavity formation energy in C_6H_6 , CCl_4 and H_2O at 298 K. Dashed lines represents correct asymptotically expression (9) and solid lines neglecting last term of expression (9).

Solubility of hard sphere: Plot of logarithm of the experimental Henry's law constant vs polarisability of the solute for a given solvent gives a reasonable smooth curve¹³. Fig. 2 shows such curve for the inert gases dissolved in benzene and water. Similar curves are obtained for all solvents. By the extrapolation technique⁸, we can determine the solubility of a hard sphere diameter 2.5Å in a particular solvent. This can be expressed as

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \ln K_H = \ln K_H^0$$

$$\sigma_2 \rightarrow 2.5 \text{ \AA}$$

Table 1. Selected physical properties of solvent at 298 K

Substance	σ_1 $\times 10^8$ cm	μ D	ϵ/k K	V_1 $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	η
C ₆ H ₆	5.26	0	496	89.4	0.513
CCl ₄	5.38	0	530	97.09	0.506
H ₂ O	2.77	1.84	79.3	18.08	0.371

*The entries found completely in Ref. 8.

Table 2. Properties and parameters for the solute^a

Solute	σ_1 $\times 10^8$ cm	ϵ/k K	$\alpha \times 10^{24}$ $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
He	2.63	6.03	0.204
Ne	2.79	35.7	0.393
Ar	3.41	125	1.63
Kr	3.67	169	2.46
Xe	3.96	217	4.00
Rn	4.23	290	5.86
N ₂	3.70 ^b	95	1.74 ^c
H ₂	2.87 ^b	29.2	0.802

^aFrom Ref. 8. ^bFrom Ref. 9. ^cFrom Ref. 10.

Table 3. Solubility and Gibbs free energy parameters of non-polar gases in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water

Solute	$\ln K_H$		ΔG_s (cal mol ⁻¹)	
	Theor.	Expt.	Theor.	Expt.
In benzene :				
He	8.89	9.48 ^a	5258	5613
Ne	7.87	6.33 ^a	4660	5436
Ar	6.33	7.05 ^a	3748	4174
Kr	5.49	5.39 ^a	3251	3511
Xe	4.73	-	2795	-
Rn	3.37	-	1995	-
In carbon tetrachloride :				
He	8.56	-	5068	-
Ne	7.53	-	4459	-
Ar	5.91	6.62 ^b	3499	3919
Kr	5.14	-	3043	-
N ₂	6.77	7.33 ^b	4008	4340
H ₂	7.83	8.15 ^b	4636	4826
In water :				
He	11.42	11.89 ^c	6762	7040
Ne	11.06	11.72 ^c	6549	6939
Ar	10.30	10.62 ^c	6099	6288
Kr	9.84	10.06 ^c	5826	5956
Xe	9.16	9.47 ^c	5424	5607
Rn	8.03	8.70 ^d	4755	5151

^aRef. 3. ^bRef. 1. ^cRef. 11. ^dRef. 12.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln K_H$ vs polarisability of inert gases in water and benzene at 298 K.

where K_H^0 is the Henry's law constant for hard sphere diameter 2.5Å. Table 4 compares the values of $\ln K_H^0$ obtained from the extrapolation techniques described by Pierotti for solvent benzene and water with the values of $\ln K_H^0$ from the theory. The agreement is excellent and represents the strong validity of equation (9) as derived from asymptotically correct expression.

Determination of effective hard sphere diameter for solvent : Since the value of $\ln K_H^0$ determined by extrapolation technique is equal to $\beta\mu_{\text{cav}}(d) + \ln(RT/V_1)$,

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0} \ln K_H = \ln K_H^0 = \beta\mu_{\text{cav}}(d) + \ln(RT/V_1)$$

$$\sigma_2 \rightarrow 2.5\text{\AA}$$

It is clear that its value is determined only by the properties of the solvent σ_1 , V_1 , T and hard sphere diameter $\sigma_2^0 = 2.5\text{\AA}$. If one takes σ_1 to be unknown, then it is possible from the intercept of the $\ln K_H$ vs α curve to determine the effective hard sphere diameter of the solvent which is given in Table 5. The agreement of the hard sphere diameter (σ) for benzene and water obtained from various source is further strong

Table 4. Theoretical and experimental values of $\ln K_H^0$

Solvent	T	$\ln K_H^0$	
		Calcd.	Obsd.
C ₆ H ₆ (5.26)	298	9.48	9.50
H ₂ O (2.77)	298	11.83	11.80

conformation for the validity of equation (9) obtained from asymptotically correct expression.

Table 5. Comparison of effective hard sphere diameter for benzene and water obtained from various sources

$\sigma_{\text{C}_6\text{H}_6}$, Å	5.24 ^a	5.22 ^b	5.27 ^c	5.26 ^d
$\sigma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, Å	2.78 ^a	2.72 ^e		

Value of $\sigma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ ranging from 2.5 to 2.93 Å (Ref. 14).

^aObtained from gas solubility in the manner describe in this paper. ^bFrom the liquid state using the equation of solute and vap. ^cFrom gas viscosity. ^dFrom the cell theory of liquid of Salasburg and Kirkwood. ^eFrom the scaled particle theory of compressibility.

The solubility of inert gases in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and water at 298 K agrees well with the experimental values. However, there is some discrepancy between the experimental and theoretical values. The solubility of gases depends of the cavity formation energy (CFE) of the solvent molecules and interaction energy (G_i) between solute and solvent. The value of hard-core diameter (σ) which is the major parameter on the determination of CFE are available in the literature. Calculated from the viscosity or diffusion coefficients, the results obtained from different experiments differ widely. So exact choice of this parameter is difficult. The difference between the experimental and theoretical values of $\ln K_H$ partly arises from that choice. Moreover, the solute-solvent interaction energy is sensitive to the values of ϵ/k , the L-J parameter. For argon, ϵ/k ranges from 117 to 125 and for benzene 440 to 504. So proper choice of ϵ/k and σ gives the exact experimental results as expected.

The method suggested here can be used to calculated the

exact hard sphere diameter and ϵ/k for the specific solute-solvent interactions. In the case of mixtures of polar and non-polar solvents, the work is in progress.

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